

Analysis of the Relationship between Quality of Life in Addition to Life Satisfaction among College Students

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Abstract:-

Purpose: The intention of the current study is to analyze the relationship between quality of life in addition to life satisfaction among college students.

Method: This descriptive-analytic revision was completed resting on 400 students (200 males and 200 females) through the telephone survey method. The investigation tools were the quality of life and satisfaction with life is deliberate. Statistics were analyzed by Pearson's correlation as well as T-tests in SPSS software.

Finding: In the present study, a significant correlation exists between the quality of life and satisfaction with life ($P < 0.05$). In the T-test outcome, the quality of life score in the middle of the male scholars in the current study is significantly added higher than that of female scholars; in addition in this container, males are additionally satisfied with their existing situation than females.

Conclusion: The result indicated that the quality of life is greater than ever in students' satisfaction with life. In order to move up the level of psychosomatic well-being, it is essential to shell out responsiveness to the quality of life in addition to life satisfaction by educating society.

Keywords:- Life satisfaction, Quality of life, and College student.

I. INTRODUCTION

Life satisfaction has been defined by Pavot & Diener, 1993 as a cognitive, global measure of the quality of life. It is an additional vigorous determination of well-being, for the reason that it reduces the amount of subject in the direction of mood fluctuations. Life satisfaction is associated with enhancing substantial health, privileged recital, as well as stronger societal interaction. How satisfied you are in the midst of your life is significantly intended designed for your welfare easier on the way on the way to respond that how happy you are, along with an additional having an important effect move toward evaluating the quality of the life. Life satisfaction is a constant in addition to inclusive thought, which reflects the wisdom as well as the whole vision of the community of society towards the humanity they are alive. Life satisfaction is an apparent indication of the victorious adjustment of a human being to changes in an assortment of circumstances. Different on the

way to general prospect, life satisfaction does not refuse by aging, as well as remaining constant all the way through the life stage. Men along with women are parallel within their whole levels of satisfaction even if women execute relation additional optimistic in addition to depressing consequences. In general, the marital group describes higher life satisfaction, and those with lifelong marriages are for the most part pleased, societal sustain is optimistically linked in the direction of life satisfaction. The citizens who entertain compassionate collective relationships in addition to helpful interpersonal interaction more often than not comprise not as much anxiety for the reason that they are happy by means of their life. It does not issue wherever the societal maintain comes on or after, be it commencing parents, peers, teachers, or else, social group, it has been revealed on the way to be allied in the midst of a far above the ground stage of life satisfaction along with the natural appeal. People who lack adequate social support and interpersonal relationships are likely to feel angry and anxious, resulting in dissatisfaction with their lives. Self-esteem can be boosted and one's life can become more meaningful when one is surrounded by supportive social networks. According to the findings of a study on life satisfaction, two important factors are heavily influencing life satisfaction: personality, and satisfaction in specific spheres of life. The level of life satisfaction is different for each personality type, according to research. Individuals who are outgoing tend to be happier in life, while those who are inward-looking are less happy in life. On the other hand, individuality lying in your possession does not give particulars of the entire narrative. Don't be up to snuff on the way to keep in mind that the manner we by the side of here evaluate persona depends on latent resting on your attitude evaluation of how you hold up, be aware of, as well as proceed within comeback on the way to the secure condition. Consequently, if you find yourself prone in direction of pondering your life in general as well as your overall health within a negative brilliance on a personality test, you will be more in danger of doing the same in health. The interchange aspect is an assortment beyond central as well as makes out of understanding. It's assumed that you will achieve a tremendous amount of life satisfaction if you are naturally satisfied with certain life. The quality of life in this sphere is influenced, among other things, by the level of satisfaction with life in this sphere. It's important to note that there still remains a caveat, and overall life satisfaction also depends on how satisfied you are in life areas that provide support. Furthermore solitary of the factors of cheerfulness is satisfaction in the midst of life.

Individualities could do with en route for being alive in actuality pleased by way of their living inside the array in the direction of subsisting pleased. Sadness among the living is capable of the crash being happiness, which is a hazardous thing in favor of self- murder. Globally, 350 million people suffer from depression, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). So, the suggestion of quality of life can be realized by creating healthiness in addition to happiness.

Quality of life is a conception that numerous attempts here the once three decades have been ended inside array to define and appraise without bias. Although in the face of an unrestrained investigation conducted resting on the quality of life, there’s no single narrative as well as agreement on the subject of it. A number of scholars describe the quality of life by means of an idea that comes within reach, in addition, to thinking about obvious belongings linked in the direction of alive norms, together with substantial health, scrupulous standing (assets, livelihood circumstances, etc.), communication, plus job-related or else further societal as well as commercial factors within the estimation of the quality of life. Here difference to this comes within reach of, there’s a personal approach, there’s a new approach, called holistic into which the proponents accept as true that quality of life, similar to life itself, is an intricate as well as multidimensional commencement, plus in the analysis, they think about in cooperation goal and personal factors.

College pupil the term “council pupil” means an existent who’s a full-time or a part- time pupil attending an institution of advanced education.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the significant relationship between quality of life in addition to satisfaction with life.
- To analyze significant differences between male and female groups in mean scores on quality of life in addition to satisfaction with life.

III. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant relationship between quality of life in addition to satisfaction with life.
- There are no significant differences between male and female groups in mean scores on quality of life in addition to satisfaction with life.

VI. RESULT

Table 1 Pearson's Correlation between the Quality of Life and Satisfaction with Life

		QOL	SWL
QOL	Pearson Correlation	1	.136
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.054
	N	200	200
SWL	Pearson Correlation	.136	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.054	
	N	200	200

IV. VARIABLES

A. Independent variables

- Gender- Male and Female

B. Dependent variables

- Quality of life
- Life satisfaction

V. METHODS

This is a descriptive- logical revision that was completed taking place 400 scholars by tale system. After carrying their concurrence to share during the study; the questionnaires were done by them. The scholars were between the ages of 20- 25 years. The exploration tools were two questionnaires. Which were used subsequent to inward-bound the exacting in the sequence of the scholar? The first questionnaire was the Quality Of Life Scale (QOLS). WHO defines the quality of life as a person's perception of their status in life in context with the culture and values they live in and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns. The Quality Of Life Scale (QOLS) was initially a 15-item tool that considered five intangible domains of quality of life: material and physical well-being, relationships with other people, social, community, and civic activities, personal development and fulfillment, and recreation. Subsequent to the evocative examination that queried people through chronic illness resting on their perceptions of quality of life; the tool was extended on the way to comprise one more item: independence, the ability to do for yourself. Therefore, the QOLS in its current format contains 16 items. Another questionnaire used in this study was Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS), which was organized by Diener et. al.(1985). It contains five statements that quantify the cognitive element of personal well-being and measure the degree of personal satisfaction with every one of the statements by a 7- point Likert scale ranging starting explosively differ (score 1) to explosively agree (score 7). Evocative in addition to deducible statistics (T-test and Pearson’s correlation) in SPSS software was used to dissect the information.

A Pearson Correlation examined the relationship between the quality of life and satisfaction with life. The mean for the quality of life was 83.01(SD= 2.273450341) and the mean for satisfaction with life was 24.71 (SD= 0.483588019). The relationship was negligible positive

correlation and statistically significant ($r=.136, <p=0.05$). Hence, the first null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. This shows that an increase in quality of life would lead to raising satisfaction with life in the followers.

Table 2 Descriptive indexes for mean and SD values of quality of life and satisfaction with life scores according to male and female

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QOL	Male	100	87.17	10.838	1.084
	Female	100	78.85	14.053	1.405
SWL	Male	100	25.36	6.777	.678
	Female	100	24.06	6.093	.609

Table 3: T-test (Independent Samples Test) results to evaluate male and female students based on quality of life and life satisfaction scores

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	DF	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
QOL	Equal variances assumed	12.423	.001	4.688	198	.000	8.320	1.775	4.820	11.820
	Equal variances not assumed			4.688	185.991	.000	8.320	1.775	4.819	11.821
SWL	Equal variances assumed	3.801	.053	1.426	198	.155	1.300	.911	-.497	3.097
	Equal variances not assumed			1.426	195.801	.155	1.300	.911	-.497	3.097

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to determine if a difference existed between the mean quality of life and satisfaction with life scores of males and females. There was statistically significant difference between the mean quality of life score of males ($M=87.17, SD= 10.838$) and female ($M= 78.85, SD= 14.053$), $t(198) = 4.688, p = .000$. The 95% confidence interval was 4.820 to 11.820. And there was statistically significant difference between the mean satisfaction with life score of males ($M= 25.36, SD= 6.777$) and female ($M= 24.06, SD= 6.093$), $t(198) = 1.426, p = .155$. The 95% confidence interval was -.497 to 3.097. Consequently, the second null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected; it means there is a significant difference between male and female groups in mean scores on quality of life and life satisfaction.

VII. DISCUSSION

In the present study, a significant correlation exists between the quality of life and satisfaction with life ($P<0.05$). Since some aspects of physical and internal health contribute to the quality of life, In addition to environmental and social health, a high score in quality of life indicates the existent is in good health; additionally, it seems only natural that one with a high quality of life would also be very satisfied. The quality of life correlates

positively with satisfaction in other aspects of life, as studies have shown. A study was done to estimate the efficacy of the plan for improving a couple's quality of life on their relationship and internal health. In the experimental group, the couples attended training to improve romantic connection, improve love magnetism, improve closeness, power-sharing, conflict resolution skills, resolve endless problems and give meaning to life. The results of another study showed that a high score on the quality of life affects job satisfaction. The interchange initiative was in the direction of analysis of the considerable distinction between a female with male clusters inside mean scores resting on quality of life and satisfaction with life.

In the T-test outcome, the quality of life score in the middle of the male scholars in the current study is significantly added higher than that of female scholars; in addition in this container, males are additionally satisfied with their existing situation than females. In further studies with reference to gender disparity, there are numerous contentious findings taking place on the relation between quality of life and life satisfaction gain. Intended for design, Saadat et. al (2010) plants refusal association stuck between the quality of life score and sexual category. In relationship by means of satisfaction, it was observed that life satisfaction; in particular instruction satisfaction is added in

girls than in boys. The distinction addicted to end result can be apposite on the way in the path of differences inside the companies deliberate similarly to within addition differences inside the apparatus used.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A person's quality of life includes cooperation delicate in addition to societal aspects that are grave for his or her health as well as well-being. Therefore, it is necessary to consider these variables and their relationships and guide youth to organize to enhance them.

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